

DECODING THE HYPE: A PRAGMATIC INVESTIGATION OF MARKETING OPPORTUNITIES WITHIN THE METAVERSE AND FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDAS

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Abstract: The advent of the Metaverse as an emergent and rapidly evolving virtual environment presents both opportunities and challenges for marketing practitioners and researchers. This literature review critically and pragmatically examines the existing body of knowledge on marketing in the Metaverse, elucidating potential research areas and topics while emphasizing the importance of adopting a balanced and sceptical approach. The review explores four key research domains: customer behaviour and engagement, ethical marketing and social responsibility, evaluation and performance measurement, and technological advances and marketing integration. By identifying constraints, biases, and areas necessitating further investigation, this review provides valuable insights for organizations navigating the uncertain terrain of the Metaverse. The paper encourages future research to delve into the long-term implications of the Metaverse, focusing on its potential impact on society, culture, and the economy. It also advocates for interdisciplinary studies that contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the Metaverse and its effects on marketing strategies and practices. By adopting a critical and pragmatic approach, this literature review aims to guide researchers and practitioners in successfully harnessing the potential of the Metaverse while mitigating risks and fostering responsible, ethical marketing practices in this dynamic virtual landscape.

Keywords: Customer Behaviour, Customer Engagement, Immersive Customer Experience, Metaverse Marketing, Ethical Marketing

1. INTRODUCTION

The Metaverse, a concept that originated in science fiction, has rapidly evolved into a highly debated and complex digital landscape. With its potential to impact various aspects of marketing, customer behaviour, and technological innovation, the Metaverse presents both opportunities and challenges for businesses. However, it is essential to maintain a critical and pragmatic approach when examining its implications on marketing practices.

This literature review objectives to provide a balanced analysis of the current research on the Metaverse, focusing on its origins, evolution, and influence on customer behaviour and engagement, while also considering the ethical implications and the role of technology in shaping marketing strategies.

As the Metaverse is predicted to transform various industries, including marketing, fashion, technology, and gaming, it is vital to explore this convergence of physical reality and

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digital virtuality (De Felice et al., 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2023; Lim, 2023; Rathore, 2023). Some proponents argue that the Metaverse will evolve the Internet into a virtual 3D social media world, offering new and captivating user experiences (Hollensen et al., 2022). However, sceptics (Robertson, 2021; MacDonald, 2022; Wankhede, 2022) argue that the Metaverse is an ill-defined concept with no tangible product or purpose, raising concerns about its legitimacy and impact.

This paper delves into the marketing implications of the Metaverse with a critical lens, aiming to provide managers and academics with a better-informed perspective. The research is centred around four key areas of scepticism:

- I. Customer Behaviour and Engagement.
- II. Ethical Marketing and Social Responsibility
- III. Evaluation and Performance Measurement
- IV. Technological Advances and Marketing Integration

Drawing on a literature review, the paper first explores the concept of the Metaverse in general and its relevance to marketing. Finally, the paper offers suggestions for future research directions, paving the way for a more comprehensive understanding of the Metaverse's potential and limitations.

The article “*A Sceptical View of Opportunities Marketing in the Metaverse*” explains the Metaverse's implications in a marketing context by taking a sceptical approach to critical categories like customer experiences, trust, engagement, and advertising. The author concludes the article by encouraging firms to be cautious and sceptical when developing any metaverse marketing strategy. As a result, there is plenty of room for trial and error before launching the final business activities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In today's competitive landscape, merely offering high-quality products and services is no longer enough, as most are homogeneous and the local and global markets fiercely compete (Israfilzade, 2021). As portrayed by media and early-stage companies, the Metaverse may seem like a futuristic concept where individuals use avatars to represent themselves, interact, build communities, and trade digital currencies for various goods and services (De Felice et al., 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2023; Lim, 2023). However, upon closer examination, one can argue that such technologies already exist and have been utilized for years, particularly in the gaming industry.

Some proponents assert that the Metaverse is the inevitable next step in the evolution of the Internet, a 3D counterpart accessible through a unified access point. However, others (Hollensen et al., 2022; De Felice et al., 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2023) contend that the Metaverse is simply an additional 3D layer built upon the traditional 2D Internet. According to Zhao et al. (2022), the Metaverse is still in its nascent stages. No research systematically summarises the technical framework for its complete visual construction and exploration, nor examines graphics, interaction, and visualization separately from the Metaverse's perspective.

By organizing the review into four key research domains, namely customer behaviour and engagement, ethical marketing and social responsibility, evaluation and performance measurement, and technological advances and marketing integration, this study offers a comprehensive examination of the current state of research in the field.

2.1. The Metaverse: Origins and Evolution

The origin of the term meta (μέτα) is Greek, and its meaning is "after, behind, among, between, modified, changed, higher, beyond." In Greek, the prefix meta- is less arcane than in

English; Greek meta- is closely related to the Latin words post- or ad-. In its most basic form, meta- characterises a topic in a way that extends and transcends its fundamental boundaries of the object or uses the subject as an object of interpretation (particularly in epistemology).

The Metaverse's roots can be traced back to science fiction literature, with the earliest concepts appearing in the works of William Gibson and Neal Stephenson. Gibson's 1984 novel (Gibson, 1984), "*Neuromancer*," introduced the idea of a worldwide computer network called "cyberspace," while Stephenson's "*Snow Crash*" (Stephenson, 1992) provided a more detailed vision of a virtual reality-based Metaverse. Furthermore, one of the novel's (Snow Crash) central elements of anxiety is the merging of ontological limits, as the Metaverse and Reality are meant to be distinct.

Early Virtual Worlds. The development of early virtual worlds, such as Second Life at 2003 and World of Warcraft at 2004, marked the beginning of the Metaverse's evolution (Kock, 2008). These platforms enabled users to interact with one another in a shared digital environment, paving the way for more advanced virtual reality systems.

The Metaverse's development has been driven by technological advancements in VR, AR, and blockchain technology. VR and AR technologies have allowed for more immersive and interactive digital experiences, while blockchain has provided secure and decentralized systems for virtual asset ownership and exchange. The gaming industry has been integral to the Metaverse's evolution, with platforms like Fortnite and Roblox popularizing shared virtual spaces (Jungherr & Schlarb, 2022).

Nevertheless, "Metaverse" did not become a common phrase until October 2021, when Facebook renamed its brand name to Meta. At that time, the business declared its intention to invest \$10 billion over the following year in technology to realise its vision of the metaverse (Rodriguez, 2021). Mark Zuckerberg, the owner of Meta (previously known as Facebook), predicts that it could take between five and ten years for the metaverse's primary capabilities to become widespread.

There is considerable controversy around the justification for this rebranding and the long-term viability of this massive investment. It is also reported (Bowman, 2023; Harrison, 2023) that companies are more concerned with promoting the potential of the metaverse rather than addressing immediate financial concerns and challenges. However, this is not the purpose of the present research, but it is obvious that Facebook sparked and highlighted this topic, attracting not only more users and developers, but also more investors and academics.

In short, technological advancement has been a driving element in the evolution of the Metaverse. Computing power, graphics rendering, and networking capabilities have all improved over time, allowing for the creation of increasingly immersive virtual environments. The widespread deployment of high-speed Internet has also enabled early adopters to interact in these virtual worlds in real-time, however, this is far from perfect and is unlikely to be acceptable to a wider audience with the current version of it.

Despite significant advancements in technology, there remain limitations that could hinder the full realization of the Metaverse. Current virtual reality and augmented reality systems still face challenges in terms of latency, processing power, and user comfort. Overcoming these limitations will require further technological breakthroughs, which may take *years* or even *decades* to materialize.

2.2. Customer Behaviour and Engagement.

A growing body of research on customer behaviour and engagement (Israfilzade & Babayev, 2020; Mittal & Bansal, 2023) has also resulted from the metaverse's expanding popularity. To gain a comprehensive comprehension of the topic, it is essential to evaluate

critically the underlying assumptions and methodologies of these studies. This literature review examines the current research with scepticism and identifies potential biases and limitations.

Although customer engagement and retention are important for business success in the metaverse (Valaskova et al., 2022), it is necessary to approach this area with a balanced perspective. Identifying the factors that contribute to customer engagement in the metaverse and considering whether these factors differ significantly from those in traditional online environments can help businesses develop effective strategies.

Customer behaviour research in the metaverse may make assumptions regarding the applicability of traditional marketing theories and consumer behaviour models to virtual environments. Given the metaverse's unique properties (Valaskova et al., 2022; Mittal & Bansal, 2023), such as the immersive nature of virtual reality and the blurred borders between reality and virtual experiences, this premise may not always hold true. Furthermore, self-reported data may be influenced by social desirability bias and faulty retention. Identifying any unique factors that drive customer behaviour in the metaverse and assessing their impact on purchasing decisions could provide valuable insights for businesses.

Building Trust and Authenticity. In the metaverse, building trust and authenticity may be important for businesses to attract and maintain a customer base (Tsai, 2022; Ramadan, 2023; Zhang et al., 2023). However, it is worth considering whether the mechanisms for establishing credibility and trustworthiness in the metaverse are fundamentally different from those in other digital spaces. Exploring the effectiveness of existing trust cues in the metaverse and their implications for marketing strategies can help businesses navigate this new environment. The literature on building customer trust and authenticity in the metaverse primarily focuses on a limited set of factors, such as user interface design and social presence (Golf-Papez et al., 2022). However, trust is a multifaceted construct that involves both cognitive and emotional aspects. By not considering the full range of factors that contribute to trust, these studies may provide an incomplete picture of the role of trust in shaping customer behaviour.

Personalization and customization in marketing refer to tailored communication and product offerings based on individual customers' preferences, behaviours, and characteristics. In virtual environments, this approach becomes increasingly relevant as it enables marketers to adapt their strategies to the unique context of the metaverse, where customers' digital identities and online interactions provide valuable insights into their preferences. Research on the effectiveness and ethical implications of personalized marketing strategies in virtual environments is still in its infancy. Despite some studies (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Rathore, 2023) highlighting the potential benefits of personalized marketing approaches, the lack of empirical evidence and the potential ethical concerns associated with personalization call for more in-depth exploration of the subject.

Lack of cultural differences research. In the metaverse, cross-cultural studies on customer behaviour frequently lack a standardised research methodology, resulting in conflicting findings and interpretations. Furthermore, the literature focuses mostly on Western cultural contexts, limiting the findings' generalizability to other cultural settings. This Eurocentric bias may obstruct a thorough understanding of culture's role in shaping consumer behaviour in virtual worlds.

Word-of-mouth and Viral Marketing. The metaverse may offer new opportunities for word-of-mouth and viral marketing (Tsai, 2022; Ramadan, 2023), but it is important to remain cautious in our expectations of the effectiveness of these strategies. Exploring the factors that influence the spread of information in the metaverse and comparing the efficacy of viral marketing campaigns in the metaverse with those in other digital spaces can help businesses make informed decisions about whether to invest in viral marketing efforts in the metaverse.

2.3. Ethical Marketing and Social Responsibility

The ethical implications of personalization, customization, and responsible marketing practices in the metaverse warrant further investigation. Businesses should focus on sustainable and green marketing, diversity, equity, and inclusion to maintain a positive reputation (Golf-Papez et al., 2022; De Felice et al., 2023). Evaluating these practices' effectiveness and their impact on consumer perceptions, loyalty, and protection can provide valuable insights, aiding businesses in developing effective strategies and promoting ethical standards in the virtual environment.

Ethical Implications. The ethical implications of personalization and customization in virtual environments warrant further investigation. One prominent ethical concern is the potential invasion of privacy (Golf-Papez et al., 2022), as the collection and usage of customers' personal data for targeted marketing efforts may infringe on their right to privacy. Moreover, the use of algorithms and artificial intelligence for personalization raises concerns related to bias and discrimination, as these technologies might inadvertently perpetuate stereotypes or unequal treatment based on customers' characteristics.

Responsible Marketing Practices. Responsible marketing practices in the metaverse are important for businesses to maintain a positive reputation and uphold ethical standards (Anshari et al., 2022). While the metaverse may present unique challenges, it is essential to remain pragmatic when assessing the implications of marketing strategies in this new environment. Evaluating the effectiveness of responsible marketing practices in the metaverse and their impact on consumer perceptions and loyalty can provide valuable insights for businesses.

Sustainable and Green Marketing. Any company that wants to thrive in the face of the current economic and environmental challenges must make environmentally conscious decisions regarding their marketing strategies and focus on green approaches (Aghayev & Israfilzade, 2022). Sustainable and green marketing in the metaverse is an area worth exploring, as businesses seek to demonstrate their commitment to environmental and social responsibility. However, it is crucial to remain cautious in our expectations of the effectiveness of these strategies in driving consumer preferences and behaviours. Comparing the impact of sustainable and green marketing initiatives in the metaverse with those in other digital environments can help businesses determine the best practices for their marketing efforts.

Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion. Promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion in the metaverse is essential for businesses to create a welcoming and inclusive environment for all users. It is important to consider whether the metaverse presents unique opportunities or challenges for businesses in fostering diverse and inclusive communities. Examining how businesses can effectively address diversity, equity, and inclusion in the metaverse can provide recommendations for creating a more inclusive digital space.

Consumer protection and advocacy are important considerations for businesses operating in the metaverse (Tsai, 2022; Ramadan, 2023; Zhang et al., 2023). Nevertheless, it is necessary to approach this area with a balanced perspective, considering whether consumer protection issues in the metaverse differ significantly from those in traditional online environments. Identifying the factors that contribute to consumer protection in the metaverse and assessing their implications for businesses can help develop effective strategies for safeguarding consumer rights and interests.

2.4. Evaluation and Performance Measurement

Measuring marketing performance in the metaverse is an important area to explore for businesses seeking to optimize their strategies in this new environment (Tsai, 2022; Ramadan,

2023). While the metaverse may offer new opportunities and challenges, it is important to remain pragmatic when assessing the marketing performance. Comparing the effectiveness of marketing performance metrics in the metaverse with those in other digital environments can help businesses identify the most relevant indicators for their marketing efforts.

Consumer sentiment analysis and *brand perception* in the metaverse can provide valuable insights for businesses looking to enhance their brand image and reputation (Li, 2022). However, it is crucial to remain cautious in our expectations of the effectiveness of sentiment analysis techniques in this new environment. Comparing the impact of sentiment analysis and brand perception initiatives in the metaverse with those in other digital environments can help businesses determine the best practices for managing their brand reputation and understanding consumer sentiment.

2.5. Technological Advances and Marketing Integration

The exploration of AI-driven marketing strategies within the metaverse presents an intriguing domain for businesses striving to optimize their marketing endeavours (Huang & Rust, 2021). While the metaverse may provide novel opportunities for AI implementation, maintaining a pragmatic outlook on the efficacy of these strategies is essential. By comparing the ramifications of AI-driven marketing initiatives in the metaverse to those in other digital environments, businesses can identify best practices for harnessing AI in their marketing efforts.

Data-driven marketing and analytics in the metaverse have the potential to yield valuable insights for businesses seeking to make informed decisions and enhance their marketing strategies. Nonetheless, it is critical to exercise caution in anticipating the effectiveness of data-driven marketing techniques within this novel environment (Huang & Rust, 2021). A comparative analysis of the impact of data-driven marketing and analytics initiatives in the metaverse and other digital environments can assist businesses in determining the most effective practices for employing data to inform their marketing decisions.

3. FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDAS

The proposed research areas and topics related to marketing in the metaverse encompass a wide range of avenues for exploration, including customer behaviour and engagement, ethical marketing and social responsibility, evaluation and performance measurement, and technological advances and marketing integration. As a result, Table 1 summarises all possible research areas, avenues, and topics.

Table 1. Future research agenda marketing opportunities within the metaverse

<i>Research area</i>	<i>Research Avenues</i>	<i>Possible research topics</i>
I. Customer Behaviour and Engagement	1. Understanding Customer Behaviour	Strategies and tools for establishing credibility and promoting positive customer experiences.
	2. Building Trust and Authenticity	Analysis of customer preferences, demographics, motivations, and social interactions.
	3. Personalization and Customization	Examining the effectiveness and potential ethical implications of personalized marketing strategies in virtual environments.

	4. Cultural Differences	A cross-cultural analysis of marketing strategies, consumer behaviour, and adaptation to diverse audiences.
	5. Customer Retention and Engagement	Identifying factors that influence long-term customer engagement and loyalty within the metaverse.
	6. Word-of-mouth and Viral Marketing	Exploring the dynamics of user-generated content and peer recommendations in shaping consumer perceptions and brand reputation.
II. Ethical Marketing and Social Responsibility	1. Responsible Marketing Practices	Developing ethical guidelines and best practices for marketing in virtual environments while balancing consumer privacy and business objectives.
	2. Sustainable and Green Marketing	Investigating strategies for promoting environmentally responsible consumption and production within virtual spaces.
	3. Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion	Examining the role of marketing in fostering an inclusive and equitable virtual environment that caters to diverse user groups.
	4. Consumer Protection and Advocacy	Assessing the potential risks and challenges in ensuring consumer rights and fair marketing practices in virtual environments.
III. Evaluation and Performance Measurement	1. Measuring Marketing Performance	Developing reliable metrics, methodologies, and frameworks for assessing the effectiveness of marketing campaigns in virtual environments.
	2. Consumer Sentiment Analysis and Brand Perception	Assessing the impact of metaverse marketing campaigns on consumer emotions, brand perception, and long-term loyalty.
IV. Technological Advances and Marketing Integration	1. AI-driven Marketing Strategies	Exploring the potential benefits, challenges, and limitations of utilizing artificial intelligence and machine learning in marketing campaigns.
	2. Data-driven Marketing and Analytics	Assessing the potential opportunities and challenges in leveraging user data for targeted marketing and performance optimization.

In the domain of ***Customer Behaviour and Engagement***, understanding customer behaviour is essential for establishing credibility and promoting positive customer experiences. Building trust and authenticity through the analysis of customer preferences, demographics, motivations, and social interactions is crucial for successful marketing strategies. The research avenues within this category also focus on personalization and customization, examining the effectiveness and ethical implications of personalized marketing strategies in virtual environments. Additionally, cross-cultural analysis, customer retention, and word-of-mouth marketing play a significant role in shaping consumer perceptions and brand reputation.

Ethical Marketing and Social Responsibility is another important area of inquiry, as it focuses on developing responsible marketing practices that balance consumer privacy and business objectives. This includes investigating strategies for promoting environmentally

responsible consumption and production, fostering diversity and inclusion, and ensuring consumer protection and advocacy in virtual environments.

Evaluation and Performance Measurement is a critical aspects of marketing research in the metaverse. Developing reliable metrics, methodologies, and frameworks for assessing the effectiveness of marketing campaigns in virtual environments is necessary for refining marketing strategies. Furthermore, understanding the impact of metaverse marketing campaigns on consumer sentiment, brand perception, and long-term loyalty is essential for optimizing marketing efforts and ensuring sustained success.

Lastly, Technological Advances and Marketing Integration focus on the potential benefits, challenges, and limitations of utilizing artificial intelligence and machine learning in marketing campaigns. Researchers can also explore the opportunities and challenges in leveraging user data for targeted marketing and performance optimization. This area of research highlights the importance of harnessing technology to enhance marketing strategies while navigating potential pitfalls and ethical concerns.

Future research should continue to explore the long-term implications of the Metaverse, focusing on its potential impact on society, culture, and the economy. Additionally, interdisciplinary studies can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the Metaverse, helping to shape its development in ways that benefit individuals and communities worldwide.

4. CONCLUSION

The Metaverse represents a multifaceted and dynamic landscape that presents both opportunities and challenges for organizations, particularly within the context of marketing. This literature review has offered a critical and pragmatic examination of the extant research on the Metaverse, underscoring the significance of adopting a balanced approach when investigating its ramifications on various dimensions of marketing. By pinpointing potential constraints, biases, and areas necessitating further exploration, this review furnishes invaluable insights for organizations traversing the uncertain terrain of the Metaverse.

It is crucial, however, to approach the Metaverse with a degree of scepticism. As an emergent phenomenon, the Metaverse is subject to the *hype, inflated expectations, and potential disappointments*. Researchers and practitioners alike should exercise caution when predicting the trajectory and impact of the Metaverse on marketing and consumer behaviour. Acknowledging its nascent status, the academic community should remain vigilant in scrutinizing the potential consequences and limitations of the Metaverse, avoiding the pitfalls of overgeneralization and unfounded claims.

Future research agendas ought to encompass a diverse range of subjects, including customer behaviour and engagement, ethical marketing and social responsibility, evaluation and performance measurement, and technological advances and marketing integration. Interdisciplinary investigations can contribute to a more holistic understanding of the Metaverse, facilitating its development in ways that are advantageous to individuals, communities, and businesses globally. Scholars should persist in exploring the long-term implications of the Metaverse, concentrating on its potential impact on society, culture, and the economy, while addressing possible ethical concerns and advocating responsible marketing practices.

In summary, the Metaverse is an expeditiously evolving domain that necessitates a critical and pragmatic approach to comprehending its implications on marketing and organizational practices. By maintaining a balanced and sceptical perspective and prioritizing future research agendas, organizations can successfully navigate the Metaverse and capitalize on its unique

opportunities to foster innovation, expansion, and enduring success, while mitigating potential risks and unforeseen consequences.

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